

COMPARISON BETWEEN B₄C/BORON AND SIC/BORON REINFORCED ALUMINIUM

H. O. LEIS

Central Laboratories of Messerschmitt-Boelkow-Blohm

P. PETERS

Deutsche Forschungs- und Versuchsanstalt fuer Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.

INTRODUCTION

The main determinants for the application of fibre-reinforced composites with a metal matrix, including in particular boron fibre-reinforced aluminium, in aircraft construction and defence engineering are the characteristics inherent in these composites and the experimental values gained during the manufacture of structural components. Despite the considerable costs incurred by such fibres, experts plan to use boron aluminium (B-Al) in hybrid structures for future missiles.

In view of its metallic properties, a metal matrix is particularly suitable for use in composites. The preferred application of B-Al over carbon-fibre reinforced plastics is justified if one of the following properties is indispensable:

- Resistance to temperatures of up to 300°C
- Resistance to lightning
- Non-combustibility and fire protection
- Good heat conduction based on the thermal conductivity
- Resistance to aggressive media (lubricants, salt spray, etc.)
- Transverse and longitudinal tensile strengths of the matrix.

At present, only one single company in the entire Western hemisphere is in a position to execute a sizable order for boron fibres within an economically viable period of time. Possessing more than 400 reactors, Messrs. AVCO in Lowell, Mass., U.S.A., produces uncoated boron fibres and under a licence agreement, granted by SNPE, France, B₄C-coated boron fibres as well.

While ceasing to produce B₄C/B fibres this year, Messrs. SNPE has taken over the sale of AVCO fibre products on the European market.

To manufacture large-sized B-Al sheets, it was necessary to undertake comprehensive studies and investigations on the basic characteristics of the B-Al material prior to its application. For this purpose, an agreement was elaborated between France and Germany, in which the willingness to cooperate in this field was expressed and a work programme set up between the persons responsible in both countries.

This programme consisted of two parts, the first part serving to determine the static mechanical properties and to examine the suitability of two unidirectionally reinforced materials (Borsic Tapes from CTI and B₄C/B-Tapes from SNPE) under aging conditions when exposed to heat treatment states T0 and T6. During the second part of the programme the following properties were determined on the same materials in state T0:

- Fatigue strength
- Resistance to crack propagation
- Weakening caused by thermocyclic fatigue
- Rain erosion sensitivity.

TEST MATERIALS AND TEST SPECIMENS

The materials analysed were as follows:

Table 1

Material	Tape Manufacturer	Matrix	Fibre	Test Sheet	Heat Treatment
W 1	CTJ (U.S.A.)	Plasma: AA-6061	SiC/B ∅	700 x 250 mm V _F 50%	T0
W 1 T		Foil: AA-4343	145 μm	5 tape layers Manufacturer: MBB	T6
W 2	SNPE (France)	Plasma: AA-6061	B ₄ C/B	700 x 250 mm V _F 50%	T0
W 2 T		Foil: AA-4343	∅ 138 μm	5 tape layers Manufacturer: MBB	T6

Test specimens and specimen dimensions

Flat tensile specimen for tests on B-Al (Pf 118.1)

Flat fatigue specimen for tests on B-Al (Pf 200.3)

2-3 layers of adhesive

Specimen for rain erosion tests (Pf 700)

B/Al
10 layers

Specimen for interlaminar shear strength
(Pf 702)

Test configuration and specimen dimensions of B-Al and hybrid B-Al/titanium for double-sided shear tests. (Pf 701)

$$\tau_s = \frac{P}{A}$$

$$d_1 = 2.84 \text{ mm}$$

$$d_2 = 4.5 \text{ mm}$$

$$= 5.5 \text{ mm}$$

B-Al PRODUCTION

Boron fibre

Prior to studying the various methods of producing boron-fibre reinforced aluminium, I wish to briefly describe the manufacture of boron filaments.

This filament is obtained through thermal decomposition of boron trichloride in hydrogen atmosphere, a tungsten filament, approx. 10 μm thick, serving as a substrate. When heating the tungsten filament to approx. 1150°C by means of resistance heating, the following reaction occurs on its surface:

At a temperature of 1150°C, the rate of deposition amounts to 4 $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$. When applying the CVD method (chemical vapour deposition), boron is deposited, forming a layer approx. 65 μm thick. The surface of the boron filaments is characterised by the typical "corn-cob structure". Methods have been developed recently in which boron is deposited on a graphite substrate. This method does not only lead to an improvement of the strength-to-weight and the modulus of elasticity-to-weight ratios, but also entails significant advantages from an economic point of view.

According to this method, a silico-methane mixture-type reactor can easily be added to the first reactor based on a boron trichloride/hydrogen mixture for boron deposition and as a result, an additional 2-3 μm thick silicon carbide layer be applied to the boron filament in one operation. We purchase boron filaments with a 4 μm thick boron carbide layer from France. Featuring an excellent oxidation stability, these insulating layers prevent a reaction of the boron with the aluminium.

Semi-finished product

There are several methods of embedding fibres in the aluminium, depending on the various applications and the conditions to be fulfilled:

- homogenous fibrous distribution in the matrix
- uniform fibrous orientation in the matrix
- adequate binding between fibre and matrix
- avoidance of heavy chemical reactions between fibres and matrix
- avoidance of mechanical damage to fibres
- production in various shapes and dimensions
- low production costs.

Semi-finished sheet products are produced in two stages. While the first stage concentrates on producing aluminium foils with a single unidirectional fibrous layer, referred to as tapes, a number of these tapes are superposed to form sheets in the second phase.

The procedures available to realize each phase are manifold, differing considerably with respect to machinery and prices involved.

The methods applied to produce these unidirectionally reinforced single-layer tapes are as follows:

- infiltration
- electro-deposition
- foil plating
- thermal spraying. (Figure 1)

Unfortunately no U.S. or European firm has taken up the development of any of these methods, although, this would be easily possible from a technological point of view to pave the way for mass production of B-Al tapes. This explains the excessive prices for such tapes, amounting to approx. 1,100 DM per m^2 .

In compliance with the Franco-German materials programme, all tapes are produced by plasma-spraying the Al-Si alloy 6061.

Two procedural approaches are applied in the final production stage during which the tapes are superposed to form sheets:

- In the U.S.A. one procedure used for tape bonding is referred to as "diffusion process". For this purpose, the tapes are placed in large-scale presses where they are exposed to a pressure of 350 bars and a temperature of 540°C.
- In Europe, on the other hand, the existing autoclave capacities are utilised, featuring dimensions of up to 12 m in length and 4 m in diameter. While the autoclave pressure attains 10 bars only, the temperature involved must be very high (up to 600°C) to ensure that the aluminium foils between the tapes, consisting of a eutectoid aluminium/silicon alloy, melt and hence entail brazing of the tapes during the cooling down phase under the application of a pressure of 10 bars. This method is termed "braze bonding" in the English language.

MACHINING AND MECHANICAL CONNECTIONS

Contrary to conventional non-reinforced materials, machining operations for further processing such as moulding, separating and connecting all anisotropic materials, prove rather complicated.

Boron fibre-reinforced aluminium, e.g., can only be separated or drilled with the aid of expensive tools such as diamond wheel or drill, laser beam, or by means of spark erosion.

It is expedient to mould B-Al semi-finished sheet products to their final shape as early as during the manufacturing process. As investigations conducted by Battelle in Frankfurt have shown, however, subsequent hot-forming of boron-aluminium is also possible under consideration of the fibrous orientation (advantage vis-à-vis fibre-reinforced plastics).

The connection of fibre-reinforced materials constitutes a particular problem, as--except for loop connections--the force introduction is interrupted in almost all cases. Boron fibre-reinforced aluminium is a suitable means for cementing materials and brazing joints if the coefficients of expansion of the materials to be cemented roughly comply with each other. Riveted and screwed connections pose no problems, either, in cross-ply tapes.

QUALITY CONTROL

For lack of a standardised quality control for B-Al, concepts must be established as early as during the development phase of such materials, reflecting one's own empirical data as well as those of other firms, in order to ensure the reliability of the products sold.

As we know today, it is not in the first instance individual fibrous ruptures that cause grave defects on the single-layer reinforced B-Al tapes, but discontinuous thickness of the fibrous insulating layer. Fibrous ruptures can easily be detected by means of radioscropy.

The most important control measure to which the tapes were subjected was the static tensile strength test conducted on individual fibres which were separated previously from the tapes by means of a 10% NaOH solution.

The results of all tests carried out on the tapes are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Fibre Type of semi-finished product	SiC/B (Borsic)	B ₄ C/B
Diameter of fibre (μm)	147-148	137-138
Spacing between fibres (fibres per cm)	55	57
Fibre content (%)	52	47
Fibrous density (g/cm ³)	2.52	2.58
Tensile strength of individual fibres (N/mm ²)*	3133	3900
Oxide content in matrix (weight-percent Al ₂ O ₃)		
a. AA-6061 plasma-spray coating	0.38	0.38
b. AA-4343 soldering foil	0.24	0.24

* Mean value from 20 measurements

STATIC PROPERTIES

Tensile strength at room temperature, -55°C, +150°C and 300°C

Based on the premises of an ideal binding between fibres and matrix, the theoretical strength and, hence, the stress σ_c in the case of unidirectionally embedded continuous fibres can be determined by totalling the stresses of matrix and fibres:

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_m \cdot V_m + \sigma_F \cdot V_F \quad (\text{law of mixture}).$$

The fibre content in boron fibre-reinforced aluminium usually amounts to approx. 50% in practice. Given a fibre strength of $\sigma_F = 4000 \text{ N/mm}^2$, the strength of the composite would have to amount to $\sigma_c = 2000 \text{ N/mm}^2$. Figure 2 shows a 20% drop in strength after plasma-spraying, which signifies that the binding conditions are optimal. The results obtained from our investigations on boron aluminium with a 50% fibre content ranged from 1370 to 1500 N/mm² (Figure 3).

The high longitudinal strength values were measured on specimens and semi-finished sheet products only, using B₄C-coated boron fibres. The transverse tensile strength measured on the same material has been relatively low so far, amounting to $\sigma_g = 75 \text{ N/mm}^2$. By changing the plasma-spraying conditions, experts recently succeeded in raising these values to 130 N/mm².

American material containing SiC-coated boron fibres features the following values:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_g &= 150 \text{ N/mm}^2 \\ \sigma_l &= 1000 \text{ N/mm}^2 \end{aligned} \quad \text{at room temperature}$$

Figure 3 also indicates the high-temperature strength of 5-layer B-Al sheets in longitudinal and transverse directions.

Tensile strength subsequent to aging under load and heat

A number of flat bars (236 x 10 mm) consisting of 5-layer B-Al sheets were suspended in a HERAEUS furnace with recirculating air and heated over a period of 1500 hours at 180°C. Following this process, the residual strength was determined in longitudinal and transverse direction at room temperature.

Moreover, flat bars featuring the same dimensions were placed in a furnace with recirculating air and subjected to a load at 150°C, corresponding to half the tensile load at room temperature. The test duration again amounted to 1500 hours.

The results of the residual strength test indicated in Table 3 only show an insignificant drop as against the initial strength.

TABLE 3

Material	Fibre Orientation	Tensile strength at room temperature N/mm ²	Tensile strength at 150°C N/mm ²
W 1	in longitudinal direction	1000	1100
	in transverse direction	95	95
W 2	in longitudinal direction	1240	1115
	in transverse direction	46	46
W 2 T	in longitudinal direction	1350	1250
	in transverse direction	70	60

Fibre content: 50 percent by volume

Tensile strength after aging under salt spray conditions

Test bars with a diameter of 236 x 10 mm were subjected to aging tests in a salt fog chamber (Figure 11). A load was applied to these test bars for a period of 750 hours, corresponding to half the tensile load at room temperature under normal conditions. Moreover, a salt fog consisting of a 5 % NaCl solution was sprayed in the chamber. The temperature in the chamber amounted to 35°C.

Following this aging process, the residual strength of the test bars was determined in longitudinal fibre direction, and, as Table 4 shows, no changes can be detected vis-à-vis the initial strength.

TABLE 4

Material	Tensile strength at room temperature σ_L (N/mm ²) after aging under application of load and salt fog	Tensile strength at room temperature (N/mm ²) prior to aging
W 1	1050	1000
W 2	1420	1370
W 2 T	1350	1350

Fibre content: 50 percent by volume

PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

Apart from the damping properties which are satisfactory in most of the composites, it is above all the thermal expansion behaviour which is of utmost importance to design engineers when judging combinations with other materials.

As Figure 4 shows, the coefficient of thermal expansion depends on fibre content and orientation.

DYNAMIC PROPERTIES

The fatigue criterion is a main determinant for many structural applications in the aerospace industry. For this purpose, the present programme provided for fatigue tests carried out in the range for pulsating tensile stresses ($R = + 0.1$) at frequencies ($f = 30$ Hz) of up to 5×10^6 N. The materials concerned were unidirectional and cross-ply B-Al materials with B₄C-coated boron fibres as well as with Borsic fibres.

Just as a number of crack propagation tests, the fatigue tests served to clarify ruptures following dynamic loads.

Fatigue strength

The staircase procedure served to determine the fatigue strength on 20 specimens per parameter by applying loads of up to 5×10^6 N. Based on the static strength, the fatigue limit was reached stepwise, the first load applied in this test amounting to 90% of the static strength. If the specimen breaks, it is replaced by a second one, whereby the overstress applied is reduced by 5-7%. This process is continued until a specimen endures 5×10^6 N. As soon as this happens, the load applied to the following specimen is raised by one step until the number of specimens tested without rupture is sufficient to permit a reliable determination of the fatigue limit. The loads applied to the remaining specimens were selected so as to obtain a complete S/N curve.

Fatigue test results

No.1 Fatigue strength exhibited by material 1, 5 tape layers, unidirectional, (UD); longitudinal fibre testing.

No.4 Fatigue strength exhibited by material 1, 6 tape layers, cross-ply (CP)
 ($0^\circ, +60^\circ, -60^\circ, -60^\circ, +60^\circ, 0^\circ$);
 Testing: Transverse in comparison with the 0° direction of the tape layer.

No.5 Fatigue strength exhibited by material 2, 5 tape layers, unidirectional, (UD);
longitudinal fibre testing.

No.8 Fatigue strength exhibited by material 2, 6 tape layers, cross-ply (CP) ($0^\circ, +60^\circ, -60^\circ, -60^\circ, +60^\circ, 0^\circ$);
 Testing: Transverse in comparison with the 0° direction of the tape layer.

As the individual results from transverse fibre testing were characterised by considerable dispersion, an S/N curve could not be plotted.

Statistical determination of the fatigue strength at 5×10^6 N

With the aid of the staircase procedure, a stress zone was approached step-by-step in which specimens were obtained with (X) and without (O) rupture. The data measured in this stress zone can be used for statistical determination of the fatigue strength σ_f including the pertaining standard deviation S.

Based on the material 2 results, item S/N curve No. 5, the fatigue strength is determined as follows:

	Over stress (N/mm ²)		<u>i</u>	<u>n_i</u>	<u>i · n_i</u>	<u>i² · n_i</u>
	929	x	4	2	8	32
Werkstoff 2	904	x	3	1	3	9
unidirectional	878	x	2	1	2	4
	852		1	0	0	0
	826		0	0	0	0
			<hr/>			
			N=4	A=13	B=45	

x = Ruptured specimens

0 = Specimens without rupture at 5×10^6 N

$$\sigma_f = \sigma_0 + d \left(\frac{A}{N} \pm \frac{1}{2} \right) \text{ and } S = 1.62 d \left(\frac{N \cdot B - A^2}{N^2} + 0.029 \right)$$

d = Difference between the stress levels;

σ_0 = Top stress level applied to specimens without rupture.

σ_f = 898 N/mm² For $d = 26$ N/mm² and the minus sign in the bracketed expression, as the number of ruptured specimens was inferior to that of the specimens without ruptures.

$$s = 30.2 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

The fatigue strength of all test material was determined on the basis of 5×10^6 N and 50 percent ruptures and reads as follows:

	Item S/N curve No.	σ_f , 50 percent (N/mm ²)
Material 1, UD, longitudinal	1	808,0
Material 1, UD, transverse	2 (not illustrated)	60,5
Material 1, CP, longitudinal	3 (" ")	237,0
Material 1, CP, transverse	4	130,0
Material 2, UD, longitudinal	5	898,0
Material 2, UD, transverse	6 (" ")	61,0
Material 2, CP, longitudinal	7 (" ")	131,0
Material 2, CP, transverse	8	138,0

Crack propagation

Material 1 (**CTI**) and material 2 (**SNPE**) which feature a fibre content of 52 and 38 percent, respectively, were subjected to a crack propagation sensitivity test at the DFVLR (Deutsche Forschungs- und Versuchsanstalt für Luft- und Raumfahrt). Both materials were designed as cross-ply materials, the layer sequence being: 0°, +60°, -60°, -60°, +60°, 0°.

The flat specimens used for the crack propagation tests were 20 mm wide and 236 mm long and featured lateral notches of 3 and 4 mm in length, or an internal hole of 3.25 mm in diameter. The grips at the ends of the specimens are the same as those used with the flat fatigue specimens.

The specimens are polished on the front and rear side close to the notch or hole, and are marked with lines spaced at 0.5 mm, in order to permit tracing the propagating cracks. A camera was used now and then to take photographs of these cracks.

The testing machine used was a 60 KN hydropulser PCQ-010.

Test results of crack propagation

Figures 5 (W1) and 6 (W2) give an impression of the progress of the cracks. Crack propagation in materials 1 and 2 is slow until the stress reaches a critical value at the tip of the crack and from then on progresses more rapidly.

THERMOCYCLIC TESTS

A basic problem in almost all structural applications of boron fibre-reinforced aluminium is the force transmission and force introduction in conventional isotropic materials. While fibre-reinforced plastics are generally combined by means of glueing, fibre-reinforced metals are normally connected by brazing.

Brazing when compared with bonding has the advantage that the shearing strength of the boundary layer between the parts to be combined is 4 - 5 times higher and that it can be applied with higher temperatures.

The thermal properties of anisotropic materials are much more problematic than those of isotropic materials, as the anisotropic effect does not only influence the strength characteristics, but also the thermal expansion (see Figure 10), in particular with respect to hybrid materials.

Large differences in the coefficients of thermal expansion lead to delaminations and heavy deformations caused by excess stresses in the material.

To characterise boron fibre-reinforced aluminium and thus composite hybrid materials, such as B-Al + titanium, it was expedient to conduct temperature cycle tests.

The experience made by all test institutes cooperating on this programme showed that the interlaminar shearing strength of hybrid composites consisting of B-Al and titanium can best be determined by means of the double-sided shear test.

A cubical specimen placed on a die (Pf 701) is subjected to a compression test by means of a male mould and sheared on both sides. The double-sided shear strength $\tau_s = P/A$ is calculated from the quotient of the max. load P and the double-sided area $A = 2(a_1 \times a_2)$ and entered in Table 5 for materials 1 and 2, both with and without thermal shock treatment.

The double-sided shear tests were carried out with the objective of testing the quality of the brazed titanium-aluminium joint prior and subsequent to the thermocyclic tests.

Both materials showed that a thermal shock treatment during which the material was immersed in hot oil (300°C) 10 times and quenched subsequently in cold water (20°C) does not affect the double-sided shear strength.

The fractures in the brazed layer of material 1 are characterised by brittleness and differ from those in material 2 as can be seen with the naked eye in Figure 7. The load time characteristics established during the compression test show that the failure of the specimens is preceded by an elongation of the material, which is, however, not caused by the deformation of the brazed layer. As the shear strength of the aluminium matrix is inferior to that of the brazed titanium/aluminium layer (cf. W1, Figure 8, and W2, Figure 9), the matrix fails first.

RAIN EROSION

The high pressure of drop impact (approx. 500 N/mm² at 1 Mach) on high-velocity all-weather missiles leads to rain erosion which has a particularly adverse effect on the fatigue strength of this material.

Apart from materials 1 and 2, the aluminium alloy 3.3214 known as ALCOA 6061 was subjected to tests under the heat treatment conditions T0 and T6 at Messrs. DORNIER. The tests were performed on the Mach 3 test rig with the erosion conditions being as follows:

Velocity of specimen:	650 m/s
Diameter of drop:	1.2 mm
Aq concentration:	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Angle of impact:	90° and 30°
Water-sprayed area:	1 cm ² at an angle of impact of 90° 1.77 cm ² at an angle of impact of 30°.

The erosion characteristics are normally defined by means of the maximum erosion rate and the incubation period read from the erosion curve. The following can be stated on comparing the incubation periods until erosion of 10 mp has been effected (see Figure 10a and b):

1. The rain erosion resistance of the B-Al materials under conditions T0 and T6 and of the non-reinforced aluminium 6061 under condition T0 is, on an average, approx. 15 times higher at an angle of impact of 30° as compared with an angle of impact of 90°. The erosion resistance of material 6061 under condition T6 is almost twice as high.
2. The variation between conditions T0 and T6 proved most significant in the matrix (factors 2.2 and 4.5, respectively). While the variation was considerable in aluminium material 1 (factors 1.5 and 1.8, respectively), it was insignificant in B-Al material 2 (factors 0.9 and 1.2, respectively).
3. The erosion resistance of the aluminium materials is 9% to 20% higher than that of the matrix material under condition T0.

The erosion resistance of the B-Al materials falls below that of the matrix material under condition T6. While it drops insignificantly only in material 1 at an angle of impact of 90° (-4%), it drops by 54% and 69% in the other materials and conditions.

Acknowledgement

The assistance of Dr. H. W. Schroeder, DORNIER, in obtaining the rain erosion data reported in this paper is gratefully acknowledged.

References

- (1) Weeton, J. W., Scala, E.: "Composites: State of the Art", Proceedings of Session, 1971, Fall Meeting, The Metallurgical Society of AIME, Detroit, Michigan.
- (2) Mayfield, J.: "New Fibres Developed for Composites", Aviation Week and Space Technology, Jan. 8, 1979.

Fig. 1: THERMAL SPRAYING

Fig. 2: STRENGTH OF FIBRES

Fig. 3: TENSILE STRENGTH OF B-AL

Fig. 4: THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF B-AL (Ref. 1)

Fig. 5: Crack propagation of material 1

Fig. 6: Crack propagation of material 2

Table 5

Material	Tape arrangement	T	τ_{SS} [N/mm ²]	Einzelprobe Nr.					
				7	8	9	10	11	12
1	unidirect. 5 tapes	+	108						
		-	103						
	cross-ply (0°±60°) x2	+	102						
		-	106						
2	unidirect. 5 tapes	+	104						
		-	110						
	cross-ply (0°±60°) x2	+	91						
		-	101						

T = Thermal shock treatment in water at 20°C and oil at 300°C; 10 cycles

- = before thermal shock treatment

+ = after thermal shock treatment

Fig. 7: Specimens after double-sided shear test (DSST)

Fig. 8: Surface of w1/Ti after DSST

Fig. 9: Surface of w2/Ti after DSST

Fig.10 a

10 mp/cm² edge life of the tested materials

- a) angle of impact: 90°
- b) angle of impact: 30°

Fig. 10 b

Fig. 11: Salt-spray chamber with load mechanism